

Preliminary Techno-economic Analysis of Nuclear Seawater Desalination System with Lithium Extraction

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803285

ABSTRACT

Nuclear energy can be paired with seawater desalination through providing electricity to reverse osmosis (RO) or low temperature cogeneration with multi effect distillation (MED). These processes potentially synergise with lithium extraction from concentrated brine via electro dialysis (ED), for which there is increasing interest given the strategic importance of lithium. This paper presents progress towards an integrated optimization model for seawater desalination. First, a model optimizing MED for a nuclear reactor with thermal energy storage (TES) is presented. Second, a framework for evaluating the conditions under which Li extraction from seawater using RO, MED and ED is presented, with a preliminary analysis of the required ED performance and Li price for economic viability, with this found to be unlikely to be economical at current Li prices, although thermal integration of MED with the nuclear reactor was found to be potentially economically viable.

Keywords: lithium, desalination, nuclear, cogeneration

1. INTRODUCTION

Over the past several decades, desalination capacity has expanded rapidly, and growth is expected to continue as populations rise and conventional freshwater sources become more stressed [1]. Seawater can be desalinated using either electrical or thermal processes. Among thermal technologies, multi-effect distillation (MED) has been widely deployed at large scale, particularly in the Middle East. However, reverse osmosis (RO), which uses electricity to drive high-pressure pumps, has become the more dominant technology globally due to improvements in membrane technologies and energy recovery devices. While MED can take advantage of the low-grade heat generated from power cycles, including from nuclear power plants, it is often economically disadvantageous compared to RO, particularly in markets where electricity is relatively inexpensive (Table I).

Table I. Energy requirements and operating ranges for common desalination processes [2]

Properties	MED	RO	ED
Electricity used (kWh/m ³)	2.0–2.5	2–4.5	0.7–5.5
Total energy used (kWh/m ³)	14.45–21.35	2–4.5	0.7–5.5

Desalination brines are enriched with dissolved minerals that, while present in trace amounts in seawater, can be concentrated to economically interesting levels. In concentrating streams from RO or MED, many of the steps required for lithium recovery are already in place, providing a natural integration point between desalination and resource recovery. Lithium extraction from seawater has become a focus of research efforts in recent years. Although the lithium concentration in seawater is only 0.18

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ppm, the total lithium content of the world's oceans is estimated at approximately 2.6×10^{11} tons [3], far exceeding land-based reserves.

Global demand for lithium increased rapidly in the early 2020s, largely driven by the expansion of electric vehicle manufacturing. Correspondingly, lithium prices rose sharply, reaching approximately \$80/kg at the end of 2022 before stabilizing near \$10/kg in recent years [4]. These trends, combined with the virtually inexhaustible supply in seawater, have motivated growing interest in developing technologies for direct extraction. Several methods have been investigated for direct recovery, including electrodialysis (ED) with selective membranes [5], demonstrating high selectivity. Because key process parameters, such as achievable lithium yield and specific electricity consumption, are not known for industrial systems, they must be assumed within plausible ranges here. Sensitivity analysis is therefore essential to evaluate how these uncertain parameters influence system performance and economics.

Both RO and MED technologies have already been co-located with nuclear power plants. For example, Diablo Canyon Nuclear Power Plant in California operates an on-site RO facility to provide purified water for plant use. While integration is generally more straightforward for RO since it requires only an electrical connection to the plant, thermal technologies like MED have also been successfully coupled with nuclear facilities. The Aktau complex in Kazakhstan demonstrated large-scale (120,000 tons/day) nuclear-desalination integration using thermal energy from the reactor to drive distillation [6].

Thermal energy storage (TES) can further enhance the flexibility and performance of nuclear-powered desalination systems. TES buffers the interaction between the power cycle and downstream desalination units, improving operational stability and safety by decoupling thermal loads. By absorbing or releasing heat as needed, TES upstream of the power cycle to follow changes in the electricity market [7, 8]. Two-tank molten salt designs separating the nuclear island from the power cycle have also been shown to maximize dispatchable output when paired with oversized turbines, particularly in renewable-heavy markets such as CAISO [9].

TES has also been widely studied in the context of desalination. In desalination systems, TES plays a complementary role by mitigating the intermittency of renewable energy inputs, enhancing capacity factors, and reducing the levelized cost of water (LCOW). A variety of system configurations have been proposed that combine power generation, desalination, and energy storage. Ref. [10]. This study shows that TES can improve MED's competitiveness compared to RO in cogeneration contexts. Another model integrates a combined cycle power plant (CCPP) with MED through a chilled water TES unit [11]. Low-temperature desalination (LTD) systems powered by solar collectors have also been studied, with TES used to buffer solar intermittency and sustain continuous operation [12].

The objective of the current work is to investigate whether the industrial feasibility of lithium extraction from seawater is enhanced through thermal coupling with nuclear reactors. To enable this, we first investigate whether thermal coupling between a nuclear reactor coupled with high temperature TES can operate in a cost-effective low temperature cogeneration mode with an MED plant [13]. This presents a potential synergy between nuclear reactors and MED, which presents a means of concentrating the brine stream that could be input into ED, potentially offering an improved value proposition for nuclear thermal seawater desalination and lithium extraction. Next, we investigate the industrial feasibility of lithium recovery from desalination brines using both electricity and thermally driven processes, determining the conditions under which MED can enter the system. Future work will combine the time dependence and technology selection models to derive an overall integrated model, determining if value stacking from TES can improve the economic viability of lithium recovery.

2. INTEGRATION OF NUCLEAR ENERGY, TES AND MED

A mixed-integer linear programming (MILP) model consisting of three interconnected sub-cycles was built, shown in Figure 1. Models are built in the Python-based optimization package Pyomo [14] and solved using the solver Gurobi [15].

Figure 1. Simplified schematic of the combined model showing nuclear reactor with TES, supercritical steam Rankine cycle, thermal extraction, and MED with TES

- Nuclear reactor with high-temperature TES supplying thermal input to the power cycle.
- Supercritical steam Rankine cycle producing electricity for the grid.
- MED system with low-temperature TES driven by extracted steam.

The impact of thermal extraction on power cycle efficiency is evaluated using a model of a supercritical steam Rankine cycle developed by White [16]. Off-design performance is evaluated to capture the reduction in thermodynamic efficiency arising from part-load operation. Electricity prices were taken from the locational marginal price (LMP) at the Diablo Canyon Power Plant node within the CAISO network [17]. The price of distillate was set to the value paid by the San Diego County Water Authority to the Claude Lewis Carlsbad Desalination Plant in 2021 [18], which was held constant throughout the year. The cost of the two-tank high-temperature TES was based on values reported in the literature [19]. The objective of the thermal storage dispatch model is to maximize the plant's net revenue over a year while minimizing capital and operational costs, accounting for penalties associated with ramping the power and desalination systems. Both high temperature and low temperature TES are two tank storage systems, one supplying heat to the power conversion cycle and the other using heat from the back end of the power conversion cycle.

This MILP provides a framework for assessing the integration of co-generation processes into nuclear power cycles using TES, accounting for both the rate-limited characteristics of individual processes and the time-dependent economic value of their outputs. The model determined optimal subsystem sizing and dispatch for both TES and MED, demonstrating that system behavior depends strongly on the relative economic value of the commodity streams. The selling price of desalinated water was found to be a key driver: as this price increases, the optimal design shifts toward continuous steam extraction from the low-pressure turbine to supply thermal energy for desalination, with TES deployed to buffer variability as the power cycle load-follows.

Turbine capacity was varied from its design value of 494 MWe up to 200% of this value in increments of 10%, with the design-dispatch optimization re-run for each case. Introducing an oversized turbine enables the system to store reactor-generated heat in TES during periods of unfavorable electricity prices and dispatch this heat during favorable price periods, thereby producing electricity above the nominal 494 MWe and allowing the system to load-follow. The optimal capacities of both TES systems scale

approximately linearly with turbine size; however, cycle-side TES capacity increases more sharply than desalination-side TES capacity. The desalination facility size remains constant across all sensitivity runs. These results indicate that larger turbine capacities make TES for both subsystems economically attractive. The capital cost of the MED facility plays a key role in this behavior, as the model increasingly relies on low-temperature storage in lieu of expanding desalination capacity.

Figure 2. Dispatch profiles for various turbine sizes

Figure 2 presents dispatch schedules for three turbine sizes. In all cases, the system exhibits both load-following and desalination. High-temperature TES and low-temperature TES operate in a complementary “saw-tooth” pattern, where one charges while the other discharges. This operation scheme enables the desalination facility to maintain near-constant production while granting the power cycle flexibility to respond to electricity price fluctuations.

3. INDUSTRIAL FEASIBILITY OF LITHIUM EXTRACTION

The lithium extraction optimization model integrates nuclear power cycles with multiple desalination processes to evaluate system-level performance under different technical and economic conditions. The framework represents a large-scale, multi-component plant in which seawater intake can be routed through RO, MED or ED units. The processes are also connected so that RO brine can become input to MED, which in turn can be in the input to ED, MED may pull steam from one or more extraction points in the power cycle model, with progressively higher extractions having a higher electricity opportunity cost. These processes are linked by logical flow constraints and mass balances that ensure consistency in water, brine, and ion streams. The model tracks both energy and material flows, with explicit representation of lithium, sodium, and chloride concentrations.

A central component of the framework is the coupling with a nuclear steam Rankine cycle, modeled on the 50 MWe NuScale small modular reactor (SMR) [20]. The power cycle was simulated in Aspen

HYSYS to generate performance curves describing the impact of steam extraction at multiple points along the turbine line [21]. These were incorporated into the optimization model to represent the effect of steam extraction on power cycle electricity output (which may be sold to the grid, used for RO and/or used for ED) and heat availability for thermal desalination. The Aspen model and possible flow of desalination technologies are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Aspen model (left) and desalination options for model to select (right)

The model is formulated as a mixed-integer nonlinear program (MINLP) rather than a MILP because it includes both binary decision variables and nonlinear relationships between system variables. While the binary variables capture process activation and logical routing, the nonlinearities arise from bilinear terms (e.g., flow–concentration products, binary–continuous interactions) and performance functions (e.g., thermodynamic cycle output and desalination recovery). These features prevent the model from being expressed purely as a linear program, necessitating a MINLP formulation.

The objective function maximizes net profit from electricity sales, freshwater production, lithium recovery, and salt sales, while accounting for capital and operating costs of the power cycle and desalination subsystems. Constraints enforce mass and energy balances, recovery ratios, ion tracking, salinity limits, and process activation logic. The energy requirements and capital costs for relevant systems are provided in Table II.

Table II. Energy Requirements and Capital Costs for Desalination Processes

Parameter	Unit	Process		
		RO	MED	ED
Heat required	kWh _{th} /m ³	0	25.0	0
Electricity required	kWh _e /m ³	4.5	1.0	3.5
Capital cost	\$/m ³ /day	500	900	200

The recovery ratio for potable water from RO is set to a fixed value. MED can optionally be used to Mass continuity defines the ion concentrations of sodium and lithium into the ED process. The yield fraction Y of Li is not known as this depends on industrial scaleup of ED. This may also trade-off with energy usage, as more recirculation may increase Y while also increasing energy usage. Here, as the recovered Li value is $Yield \times Price$, we sweep on this combined parameter, along with the electricity required, to provide a zone of economic feasibility for a scaled-up ED process.

Figure 4 shows the feasibility zone for commercial-scale lithium extraction from seawater. In this implementation, RO, MED and ED can enter the system. The x-axis represents the specific electricity requirements of the extraction process, while the y-axis shows the product of lithium yield and per-kilogram price. This formulation was chosen to reflect equivalent economic value across different combinations of yield and price; for example, a 50% yield at a price of \$1,000 per kg is economically equivalent to a 100% yield at \$500 per kg. It is noted that there are some discontinuities in the solution which are due

to the optimizer sometimes finding a local minimum. The overall trends are however very clear, and the model is very fast running.

Figure 4. Feasibility zone for commercial scale seawater extraction of lithium

Under reference conditions, MED is selected by the optimizer and in some cases the concentrate from this supplies the ED. However, for the reference ED electricity requirement of 3.5 kWh/m^3 , the product of lithium price and yield must be around \$500, significantly higher than current prices, for lithium to be recovered economically. When lithium recovery enters the system, the optimal MED capacity increases slightly. This is because it becomes economical to extract steam from a slightly higher temperature extraction point, diverting more of the steam from the power cycle at a slightly greater relative opportunity cost of electricity production.

The MED is slightly more economic than RO under reference conditions in large part due to the thermal coupling being efficient under the assumed conditions; there is only a small opportunity cost of electricity production in using low quality steam to supply the MED. If the RO energy requirement is reduced to 2.0 kWh/m^3 , it displaces MED from the system. The ED energy usage/lithium price threshold under which lithium is extracted remains similar (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Feasibility zone for commercial scale seawater extraction of lithium at lower RO energy usage

A trade study was performed where the RO electricity cost was varied. In this study, the Li price is set to \$700 (assuming perfect recovery), which is again high relative to current prices but is useful for demonstrating behavior of the model. For the conditions analyzed, RO became economic at an electricity requirement of 3 kWh/m^3 . Meanwhile, Li recovery occurred for Li prices below a threshold in the ED electricity requirement. The optimal MED capacity varies in an interesting way depending on whether RO and/or ED are in the system as shown in Figure 6. At very low ED and RO prices, it is

knocked out of the system. At higher ED prices, it is used as a secondary step after the RO to extract further water (and potentially concentrate the feed further for ED). At high RO prices and high ED prices, MED is used in isolation for desalination. High RO prices and low ED prices lead to the highest MED build, as its capacity is maximized to supply concentrated feed to the ED.

Figure 6. Variation of RO, MED and ED deployment depending on electricity requirements

4. CONCLUSIONS

The baseline analysis of lithium extraction from seawater using electricity from RO indicates that a price of around \$700 per kg is required for lithium extraction to enter the system, an order of magnitude greater than the price spike in 2022. Depending on process efficiency, the stream could be pre-concentrated with RO and/or MED. Even this assumes aggressive process parameters for ED, with high yields and low electricity usage. For a nuclear reactor performing variable dispatch using a high temperature TES, it was found that use of low temperature TES coupled with MED enabled optimized usage of an MED desalination facility for best overall economics. This presents an opportunity for value stacking with TES, RO, MED and ED for seawater lithium mining, which may reduce the lithium price at which seawater lithium extraction becomes worthwhile. This will be investigated in future work.

5. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work has been funded under the Department of Energy's Nuclear Energy University Program contract number DE-NE0009379.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Williams. "Desalination in the 21st century: a critical review of trends and debates." *Water Alternatives*, **volume 15**(2), pp. 193–217 (2022).
- [2] M. Khan, R. S. Al-Absi, M. Khraisheh, and M. A. Al-Ghouti. "A better understanding of seawater reverse osmosis brine: Characterizations, uses, and energy requirements." *Case Studies in Chemical and Environmental Engineering*, **volume 4**, p. 100165 (2021).
- [3] J. L. Mero. "Mineral resources of the sea." *Elsevier Oceanography Series (Netherlands) eng no 1* (1965).
- [4] T. Economics. "Lithium - Price - Chart - Historical Data - News." URL <https://tradingeconomics.com/commodity/lithium>.
- [5] S. Gmar and A. Chagnes. "Recent advances on electrodialysis for the recovery of lithium from primary and secondary resources." *Hydrometallurgy*, **volume 189**, p. 105124 (2019).

- [6] "Experience gained in the operation and maintenance of the nuclear desalination plant in Aktau, Kazakhstan."
- [7] C. Forsberg, S. Brick, and G. Haratyk. "Coupling heat storage to nuclear reactors for variable electricity output with baseload reactor operation." *The Electricity Journal*, **volume 31**(3), pp. 23–31 (2018).
- [8] M. Aunedi, A. A. Al Kindi, A. M. Pantaleo, C. N. Markides, and G. Strbac. "System-driven design of flexible nuclear power plant configurations with thermal energy storage." *Energy Conversion and Management*, **volume 291**, p. 117257 (2023).
- [9] R. M. Saeed, A. Shigrekar, K. L. Frick, D. M. Mikkelson, and S. M. Bragg-Sitton. "Use Cases and Model Development of Thermal Storage Coupling for Advanced Nuclear Reactors." Technical report, Idaho National Laboratory (INL), Idaho Falls, ID (United States) (2022).
- [10] P. Sharan, T. Neises, J. D. McTigue, and C. Turchi. "Cogeneration using multi-effect distillation and a solar-powered supercritical carbon dioxide Brayton cycle." *Desalination*, **volume 459**, pp. 20–33 (2019).
- [11] V. Gadhamshetty, V. G. Gude, and N. Nirmalakhandan. "Thermal energy storage system for energy conservation and water desalination in power plants." *Energy*, **volume 66**, pp. 938–949 (2014).
- [12] V. G. Gude, N. Nirmalakhandan, S. Deng, and A. Maganti. "Low temperature desalination using solar collectors augmented by thermal energy storage." *Applied Energy*, **volume 91**(1), pp. 466–474 (2012).
- [13] E. Keith, B. Lindley, and M. J. Wagner. "Optimized dispatch and component sizing for a nuclear-multi-effect distillation integrated energy system using thermal energy storage: E. Keith et al." *Optimization and Engineering*, **volume 26**(2), pp. 913–938 (2025).
- [14] W. E. Hart, J.-P. Watson, and D. L. Woodruff. "Pyomo: modeling and solving mathematical programs in Python." *Mathematical Programming Computation*, **volume 3**(3), pp. 219–260 (2011).
- [15] Gurobi Optimization, LLC. "Gurobi Optimizer Reference Manual." (2024). URL <https://www.gurobi.com>.
- [16] B. T. White. "THERMODYNAMIC CYCLE MODELING OF INTEGRATED LEAD-COOLED FAST REACTOR AND CONCENTRATING SOLAR POWER." (2022). Master's Thesis.
- [17] CAISO. "Open Access Same-Time Information System." (2023). URL <http://oasis.caiso.com/mrioasis/logon.do>.
- [18] SDCWA. "SEAWATER DESALINATION The Claude "Bud" Lewis Desalination Plant and Related Facilities." (2020).
- [19] G. J. Soto, B. Lindley, T. Neises, C. Stansbury, and M. J. Wagner. "Dispatch optimization, system design and cost benefit analysis of a nuclear reactor with molten salt thermal storage." *Energies*, **volume 15**(10), p. 3599 (2022).
- [20] L. NuScale Power. "NuScale standard plant design certification application." *Chapter 10: Steam and Power Conversion System* (2020).
- [21] Aspen Technology, Inc. "Aspen HYSYS." (2021). URL <https://www.aspentech.com/en/products/engineering/aspen-hysys>.